

Case 1: Class II Div 2 Case

Dr. Devinder Preet Singh

A fifteen year old male patient reported to the dental clinic with a chief complaint of irregular upper front teeth. Intraorally the patient had Class II molar and canine relationship, division 2 incisors with deep overbite. The patient was skeletal Class II with deficient mandible. The patient was treated with comprehensive fixed mechanotherapy with self ligating metal brackets having 0.022" slot. After leveling and alignment of the teeth which took about 9 months, the patient was given Forsus Fixed Functional Appliance, to stimulate the growth of the mandible, for 6 months to correct the skeletal Class II. The total treatment took about 1.5 years with the achievement of Class I molar and skeletal relationship and ideal overjet and overbite. Permanent lower bonded retention from canine to canine was given with upper removable anterior inclined plane to retain the Class II correction.

Extra-oral Photographs (Pre-Treatment)

Frontal View

Smiling View

Profile View

Intra-oral Photographs (Pre-Treatment)

Right Lateral

Left Lateral

Frontal View

Maxillary Occlusal

Mandibular Occlusal

OPG (Orthopantomogram)

Lateral Cephalogram

Intra-Oral Photographs (Forsus Appliance)

Frontal View

Left Lateral

Right Lateral

Extra-oral Photographs (Post-Treatment)

Frontal View

Smiling View

Profile View

Intra-oral Photographs (Post-Treatment)

Right Lateral

Left Lateral

Frontal View

Maxillary Occlusal

Mandibular Occlusal

OPG (Orthopantomogram)

Lateral Cephalogram

Case 2 Anterior Crossbite

A twenty two year old female patient reported to the dental clinic with a chief complaint of irregular upper front teeth. Intraorally the patient had Class I molar and canine relationship with anterior crossbite irt. 11-41, 21-31 and rotated 12,22, 32,42. The patient was skeletal Class I with horizontal growth pattern. The patient was treated with comprehensive fixed mechanotherapy with conventional metal brackets having 0.022” slot. The leveling and alignment of the teeth took about 9 months with the correction of anterior cross bite.. The total treatment took about 1.2 years with the achievement of Class I incisor relationship and ideal overjet and overbite. Permanent lower bonded lingual retention from canine to canine was given with upper Hawley’s retainer.

Extra-oral Photographs (Pre-Treatment)

Frontal View

Smiling View

Profile View

Intra-oral Photographs (Pre-Treatment)

Right Lateral

Left Lateral

Frontal View

Maxillary Occlusal

Mandibular Occlusal

OPG (Orthopantomogram)

Lateral Cephalogram

Extra-oral Photographs (Post-Treatment)

Frontal View

Smiling View

Profile View

Intra-oral Photographs (Post-Treatment)

Right Lateral

Left Lateral

Frontal View

Maxillary Occlusal

Mandibular Occlusal

OPG (Orthopantomogram)

Lateral Cephalogram

Exponent International New Delhi
22 to 24 December 2023

54th Kerala State Dental Conferences
5-6-7 January 2024
Saptha Resorts & Spa, Wayanad

74th IDC Kolkata 2024
2-3-4 February 2024
Biswa Bangla Convention Centre Kolkata

UAE International Dental Conference
Dubai AEEDC-DUBAI
6-7-8 February 2024
Dubai World Trade Centre

Dental South China International Expo
3-4-5-6 March 2024
Guangzhou City, China

Exponent Chennai
16-17 March 2024

International Conference of Digital
Dentistry Digitize 2.0
5-7 April 2024
Le Meridian New Delhi

Exponent Kolkata
6-7 April 2024

IDEM Singapore 2024
19 20 21 April 2024

Exponent Lucknow
20-21 April 2024

IDEX Istanbul 2024
8-9-10-11 May 2024

Expo Dental Meeting Rimini, Italy
16-17-18 May 2024

SIDEX 2024 Seoul, South Korea
7-8-9 June 2024

China Dental Show
11 12 13 September 2024
Shanghai National Convention & Exhibition
Centre, Shanghai, China

World Dental Show
26-27 October 2024 Mumbai

6th Global American Academy of Implant
Dentistry & World Congress for Oral
Implantology Conference 2024
8th - 10th November 2024
The Leela Ambience Convention Hotel, New Delhi

Global Summit on Pediatrics Dentistry
30-31st December at Bangalore

IDS Germany Cologne
25 26 27 28 29 March 2025

Event Talk